

ISic1054

I.Sicily inscription 1054

Language

Ancient Greek

Type**Material**

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, Museo Iudica

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR109505

1. καὶ σύ

Edition: PHI140533

1. καὶ σύ.

2.

Edition: PHI175428

1. καὶ σύ.

2.

Edition: PHI333353

1. καὶ σύ²⁶σοί²⁶.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284836

EDR 109505
EDCS 39102208
PHI 140533
PHI 175428
PHI 333353

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0233 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 46.1249
Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5464
Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.18 ph

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